

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1870	Sarah T. Barrows	1912	No	1949	w	American phonetician	1870-1952
1870	Wilhelm Spiegelberg	1891	1891	1930		German Egyptologist (analyses of Demotic and hieratic text)	1870-1930
1870	Hubert Pernot	1892	1893	1938		French linguist, specializing in Modern Greek studies	1870-1946
1870	Albert Bernhardt Faust	1892	1892	1938		American German and German-American studies scholar	1870-1951
1870	Abdul Haq	1893	No	1930		Indian scholar and a linguist	1870-1961
1870	Hermann Schöne	1893	1893	1935		German classical philologist	1870-1941
1870	Rudolf Pöch	1895	1895	1921		Austrian doctor, anthropologist, and ethnologist	1870-1921
1870	Hugo Paul Thieme	1897	1897	1940		American literary critic, bibliographer	1870-1940
1870	Otto von Friesen	1898	1898	1935		Swedish linguist, runologist and professor of the Swedish language	1870-1942
1870	Clark Wissler	1901	1901	1942		American anthropologist	1870-1947
1870	Satish Chandra Vidyabhusan	1901	1908	1920		Indian Bengali scholar of Sanskrit and Pali Language and principal of Sanskrit College	1870-1920
1870	Torii Ryūzō	1902	1922	1951		Japanese anthropologist, ethnologist, archaeologist and folklorist	1870-1953
1870	Albert Sechehaye	1904	1905	1946		Swiss linguist	1870-1946
1870	Henry Cecil Kennedy Wyld	1905		1945		British English lexicographer and philologist	1870-1945
1870	Félix Gaffiot	1906	1906	1937		French philologist and teacher	1870-1937
1870	Charles H. Beeson	1907	1907	1935		American classical scholar	1870-1949
1871	Martha Warren Beckwith	1918	1918	1938	w	American folklorist and ethnographer, the first chair in Folklore established in the U.S.	1871-1959
1871	Otto Dempwolff	1891	1892	1911		German physician, linguist and anthropologist	1871-1936
1871	William Cunningham Smith	1891	1891	1938		American academic of English literature, university administrator, and writer	1871-1943
1871	Sarat Chandra Roy	1892		1916		Indian Bihari speaking scholar of anthropology	1871-1942
1871	Nicolae Iorga	1893	1893	1918		Romanian historian, politician, literary critic, memoirist, poet and playwright	1871-1940
1871	Ahatanhel Krymsky	1894		1941		Ukrainian Orientalist, linguist and polyglot (knowing up to 35 languages), literary scholar, folklorist, writer, and translator	1871-1942

1871	Grafton Elliot Smith	1895	1895	1927	Australian-British anatomist, Egyptologist and a proponent of the hyperdiffusionist view of prehistory	1871-1937
1871	Karl Helm	1895	1895	1936	German medievalist, Germanist and religious studies scholar	1871-1960
1871	Miguel Asín Palacios	1896	1896	1944	Spanish scholar of Islamic studies and the Arabic language, and a Roman Catholic priest	1871-1944
1871	George Bolling	1897	1897	1931	American linguist	1871-1963
1871	Carlo Formichi	1897		1941	Italian orientalist and Sanskrit Scholar	1871-1943
1871	Jean Clédat	1898		1943	French Egyptologist, archaeologist and philologist	1871-1943
1871	Leo Wiese	1899	1899	1929	German Romance philologist and medievalist	1871-1929
1871	George T. Flom	1900	1900	1939	American professor of linguistics	1871-1960
1871	Thomas Callan Hodson	1900	No	1939	British the first William Wyse Professor of Social Anthropology	1871-1953
1871	Garabet Ibrăileanu	1900		1934	Romanian-Armenian literary critic and theorist, writer, translator, sociologist	1871-1936
1871	Harriet Boyd Hawes	1901	1901	1936 w	American pioneering archaeologist, nurse, and relief worker	1871-1945
1871	Hildegarde Beatrice Hinde	1901	No	1915 w	British anthropologist	1871-1959
1871	Lionel Barnett	1902		1936	British English orientalist	1871-1960
1871	Nicholas Adontz	1908	1908	1941	Armenian historian, specialist of Byzantine and Armenian studies, and philologist	1871-1942
1872	Richard Irvine Best	1913	No	1956	Irish scholar who specialised in Celtic Studies	1872-1959
1872	Winifred Blackman	1916		1939 w	British egyptologist, archaeologist and anthropologist, one of the first women to take up anthropology as a profession	1872-1950
1872	Rudolf Helm	1892	1892	1948	German classical philologist	1872-1966
1872	Carlo Alfonso Nallino	1893		1938	Italian orientalist	1872-1938
1872	Carl Anton Baumstark	1894	1894	1935	German Orientalist, philologist and liturgist	1872-1948
1872	Robert Lehmann-Nitsche	1894	1894	1930	German anthropologist	1872-1938
1872	Georges Maspero	1894		1930	French sinologist	1872-1942
1872	Eleanor Purdie	1896	1896	1923 w	British philologist and the first woman to obtain a doctorate from the University of Fribourg	1872-1929
1872	Nikola Vulić	1896	1896	1938	Serbian historian, classical philologist, prominent archaeologist	1872-1945

1872 Kirsopp Lake	1896		1937	British English New Testament scholar, Church historian, and Winn Professor of Ecclesiastical History	1872-1946
1872 Louise Pound	1896	1900	1945 w	American distinguished folklorist, linguist, and college professor, and sportswomen	1872-1958
1872 Karl Vossler	1897	1897	1946	German linguist and scholar, and a leading Romanist	1872-1949
1872 François Thureau-Dangin	1898		1928	French archaeologist, assyriologist and epigrapher	1872-1944
1872 William Marçais	1898	1898	1942	French Orientalist, particularly noted as an expert on the Maghrebi Arabic dialects	1872-1956
1872 Elizabeth Hazelton Haight	1899	1909	1942 w	American classical scholar and academic who specialised in Latin teaching	1872-1964
1872 Henri Quentin	1900		1935	French Benedictine monk and philologist specializing in biblical texts and martyrologies, the creator of an original method of textual criticism	1872-1935
1872 Edwin Mims	1900	1900	1942	American university Professor of English literature	1872-1959
1872 Raymond Herbert Stetson	1901	1901	1939	American speech scientist	1872-1950
1872 Maurice Fishberg	1901		1934	Ukrainian-American Jewish physical anthropologist who specialised in the ethnology of the Jews	1872-1934
1872 Samson Eitrem	1902	1903	1945	Norwegian philologist, an expert in ancient literature, religion and magic	1872-1966
1872 Leonhard Schultze-Jena	1904		1937	German explorer, zoologist, and anthropologist known for his explorations of German Southwest Africa and New Guinea, as well as for his studies on Mesoamerican languages	1872-1955
1872 Edmond Destaing	1905		1940	French orientalist Arabist, Berberologist, and first holder of the Chair of Berber at the Institut national des langues et civilisations orientales	1872-1940
1872 Charles Partridge	1905		1927	British English anthropologist and historian with a particular focus on Suffolk, and former colonial administrator in Nigeria	1872-1955
1872 Shirley Jackson Case	1908	1908	1938	Canadian mathematician, historian of early Christianity, and liberal theologian	1872-1947
1872 Darnley Naylor	1909		1927	British-Australian academic who became Emeritus Professor of Classics in the University of Adelaide	1872-1945
1873 Howard R. Driggs	1910	1926	1942	American English professor	1873-1963
1873 Emilie Demant Hatt	1910 No		1940 w	Danish artist, writer, ethnographer, and folklorist	1873-1958

1873 Charles Gabriel Seligman	1910 No		1934	British physician and ethnologist	1873-1940
1873 Hilda Lorimer	1912 No		1939 w	British classical scholar	1873-1954
1873 Ovid Densusianu	1892	1892	1938	Romanian poet, philologist, linguist, folklorist, literary historian and critic	1873-1938
1873 Stanley Arthur Cook	1894		1938	British Regius Professor of Hebrew at the University of Cambridge	1873-1949
1873 Leo Frobenius	1894 No		1938	German ethnologist and archaeologist and a major figure in German ethnography	1873-1938
1873 Jeremiah D. M. Ford	1896	1897	1943	American the Smith Professor of the French and Spanish Languages and Literature	1873-1958
1873 Dmitry Abramovich	1896		1955	Ukrainian literary historian and literary scholar, philologist, paleographer, academic lecturer, publicist and writer	1873-1955
1873 Matteo Bartoli	1897		1946	Italian linguist	1873-1946
1873 David Prescott Barrows	1897	1897	1943	American anthropologist, explorer, and educator	1873-1954
1873 Wilhelm Schubart	1897	1897	1952	German ancient historian	1873-1960
1873 Emil Ermatinger	1897	1897	1943	Swiss professor for Germanic philology	1873-1953
1873 George Rapall Noyes	1898	1898	1943	American Professor of Slavic Languages	1873-1952
1873 John R. Swanton	1898	1900	1944	American anthropologist, folklorist, and linguist who worked with Native American peoples throughout the United States	1873-1958
1873 Alette Schreiner	1899	1899	1935 w	Norwegian researcher (cytology and physical anthropology)	1873-1951
1873 Franz Weidenreich	1899	1899	1941	German Jewish anatomist and physical anthropologist who studied evolution	1873-1948
1873 Ilie Bărbulescu	1899	1899	1938	Romanian linguist and philologist who specialized in the Slavic languages	1873-1945
1873 Charles Huntington Whitman	1900	1900	1937	American noted scholar of Edmund Spenser and early English verse	1873-1937
1873 Alfred Bel	1900 No		1935	French orientalist and scholar of Arab culture	1873-1945
1873 René Martial	1900	1900	1944	French medical doctor and anthropologist during the thirties and the Vichy era (1940–1944)	1873-1955
1873 Caroline Furness Jayne	1901		1909 w	American ethnologist	1873-1909
1873 Yamada Yoshio	1902		1933	Japanese linguist	1873-1958
1873 William Thalbitzer	1904	1904	1943	Danish philologist and professor of Eskimo studies	1873-1958

1873 Robert Vane Russell	1904 No		1915	British civil servant, known for his role as Superintendent of Ethnography for what was then the Central Provinces of British India	1873-1915
1873 Pierre Lacau	1904		1947	French Egyptologist and philologist	1873-1963
1873 Charles Talbut Onions	1904		1965	British English grammarian and lexicographer and the fourth editor of the Oxford English Dictionary	1873-1965
1873 Osborn Bergin	1905	1906	1940	Irish scholar of the Irish language and early Irish literature, who discovered Bergin's Law	1873-1950
1873 Makereti Papakura	1905	1930	1930 w	New Zealander (Maori) guide, entertainer and ethnographer	1873-1930
1873 Johannes Carl Andersen	1907		1937	New Zealand clerk, poet, ethnologist, librarian, editor and historian	1873-1962
1873 María Goyri de Menéndez Pidal	1909	1909	1939 w	Spanish Hispanist, literary critic, researcher, educator and advocate for women's rights	1873-1955
1873 Dmitry Ushakov	1910		1941	Russian philologist and lexicographer	1873-1942
1874 Alison Hingston Quiggin	1910		1942 w	British anthropologist	1874-1971
1874 Jacob Linzbach	1916		1941	Estonian linguist	1874-1953
1874 Father Berard Haile	1928	1951	1954	American <i>Franciscan priest</i> and one of the foremost authorities on Navajo anthropology	1874-1961
1874 Erich Berneker	1895	1895	1937	German linguist, Slavacist and Balticist, follower of the Neogrammarian school	1874-1937
1874 Eduard Schwyzer	1897	1897	1939	Swiss Classical philologist and Indo-European linguist, specializing in Ancient Greek and Greek dialects	1874-1943
1874 John Samuel Kenyon	1897	1898	1944	American linguist	1874-1959
1874 Berthold Laufer	1897	1897	1934	German-American anthropologist and historical geographer with an expertise in East Asian languages	1874-1934
1874 Max Dvořák	1897	1897	1921	Czech-Austrian art historian	1874-1921
1874 Moses Schorr	1898	1898	1938	Polish historian, politician, Bible scholar, assyriologist and orientalist	1874-1941
1874 Louis Laloy	1900		1941	French musicologist, writer and sinologist	1874-1944
1874 F. M. Cornford	1900		1939	British English classical scholar and translator known for influential work on ancient philosophy, notably Plato, Parmenides, Thucydides, and ancient Greek religion	1874-1943

1874	Lewis Spence	1900		1951	British Scottish journalist, poet, author, folklorist and occult scholar	1874-1955
1874	Raymond Wilson Chambers	1900		1942	British literary scholar, author, and academic	1874-1942
1874	James M. Farr	1901	1901	1934	American university professor and academic administrator	1874-1958
1874	Josef Horovitz	1902		1931	German Jewish orientalist	1874-1931
1874	Konstantinos Amantos	1903	1903	1939	Greek Byzantinist	1874-1960
1874	Louis-Joseph Delaporte	1903	1903	1924	French archaeologist and Hittitologist	1874-1944
1874	Paul Zarifopol	1904	1904	1934	Romanian literary and social critic, essayist, and literary historian	1874-1934
1874	Samuel A. Tannenbaum	1908	No	1943	Hungarian-American literary scholar, bibliographer, and palaeographer, best known for his work on William Shakespeare and his contemporaries	1874-1948